

ER4STEM CONFERENCE PLAN [DELIVERABLE 3.4]

ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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DISCLAIMER

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

1.1 ROLE/PURPOSE/OBJECTIVE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This document presents the ER4STEM conference plan, which is derived from the ECER organization within WP3. The purpose is to provide a generic plan on how to organize a student conference. Thus, organizers have guidelines that they can follow, even though the intended event might differ from the ECER organized within WP3.

1.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES

This document is connected with D3.1, D3.2, and D3.3, which contain the reports and proceedings of the ECER issues 2016, 2017 and 2018.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

Section 2 describes the organization of ECER as example process for obtaining experiences. Section 3 reports on the derived generic organization process for such student conferences. The remaining sections give a conclusion and provide a glossary as well as references.

2 ECER AS EXAMPLE PROCESS

2.1 DESCRIPTION

The European Conference on Educational Robotics (ECER) is an international scientific robotics conference for students, commonly aged 15-19 years. The ECER provides an opportunity for them to prepare and present their artefacts and ideas to each other and also to professional research scientists. The basic idea is to provide a chance for the students to show what they have been empowered to achieve.

The ECER is a yearly event, which was organised in the frame of the project ER4STEM in the years 2016, 2017 and 2018. The ECER took place in:

- 2016: Vienna, Austria
- 2017: Sofia, Bulgaria
- 2018: Qawra, Malta

These three issues of ECER involved the following activities for the participating students:

- Robotics competitions/tournaments:
 - Botball tournament: Botball is an educational robotics program that focuses on engaging middle and high school aged students in team-oriented robotics competitions. The Botball program has been active since 1998 and features a robotics curriculum which focuses on designing, building and programming a pair of autonomous robots. Teams use a standardised kit of materials and document the process. All materials in the kits are exactly the same for every team around the world, so there is no unfair advantages. Each set comprises two robotics controllers, an iRobot by Create, as well as metal and Lego parts. Only Botball sets are allowed in this tournament and the game rules are provided by KIPR during the Botball Instructors' Summit. KIPR develops the annual rules in the time before this summit. The tournament at ECER represents the official European Championship in Botball. A special form within the Botball tournament (which is also used for the Open tournament) are the alliances rounds for all those teams, which do not reach the finals. In the alliances, always two teams are grouped to form an alliance team and then tries to score as much as possible.
 - Open tournament: The Open tournament uses the same rules and game table as in the Botball tournament. However, participating teams may use any robotics set, rather than being restricted to the standardised Botball set.
 - Aerial tournament: This tournament does not require a game table but a setting for using drones. The common aim of this tournament was to land a drone at different zones in the game area. Specific rules applied for the robot construction.
 - Underwater tournament: This trial workshop/tournament uses a small 3D-printed submarine developed by a student employed by PRIA. The Hedgehog controller (further developed in ER4STEM WP5) was used for controlling the vessel. The aim of this tournament was to have the submarine collect small balls in a small pool and avoid obstacles while doing so.
- Student paper submissions and talks: Students had the opportunity to submit scientific papers according to the provided call for papers within a certain deadline before the conference.

These papers were reviewed and could be improved as a final submitted version. A certain amount of papers each year was chosen to be presented by the students at the conference. Some of these papers were even presented in a special session at the International Conference on Robotics in Education (RiE), which is meant for adult researchers active in the field of educational robotics.

- **Invited talks:** Each ECER involved invited talks by professional researchers of various robotics fields. Thus, the students had the opportunity to grasp current research concepts in those fields of robotics. In some cases, these researchers also participated as judges for the robotics competition. Additionally, representatives from robotics companies were invited to present their activities and bring existing robots on site.
- **Visiting RiE:** Besides, in all three years of ER4STEM, ECER was carried out in accordance with that year's issue of the International Conference on Robotics in Education (RiE). The RiE is a conference for researchers being active in the field of educational robotics. The RiE was established in 2010 in the frame of the EU project 'Centrobot' and has been organised every year since then. As RiE was carried out in parallel to ECER, the high school students were able to visit the sessions of RiE and thus could attend more scientific talks.
- **Be part of the audience:** Apart from taking part in the activities, the students but also non-participating visitors (e.g. school classes of primary or lower secondary schools) can view the competitions or talks as audience.

2.2 PREPARATION

Preparation was generally split into two phases for all ECER events: Phase 1 taking place in September to December in the year prior to the ECER and Phase 2 in the following January to April.

The performed tasks in Phase 1:

- **Setup of ECER Website:** A website was set up providing information about the conference. The website also included a form allowing the registration of participants, a Call for Papers and a link to the paper submission tool (Open conference tool).
- **Finding sponsors:** As ECER itself was covered by ER4STEM, the intention was to find sponsors mainly for financing the material costs of participating teams. Each participating country and the teams searched for sponsors on their own. However, in 2017 sponsors were also acquired for covering the costs of the venue.
- **Organisation of venue:** The local organizer was always responsible for finding an appropriate venue for ECER, so this task was performed 2016 by PRIA, 2017 by ESI CEE and 2018 by AL. The main requirement for the venue was the size, as at ECER the participating teams have the chance to actively work on their robots. Consequently, working spaces must be provided for all teams besides of the actual tournament space as well as the possibility to carry out talks. While ECER 2017 in Sofia, Bulgaria was carried out in one large hall, the venue of ECER 2018 in Malta was the ground floor of a hotel offering one large hall and several smaller rooms as well as a private restaurant area. The organizers had to adapt to the varying layout of the venue but all settings were successful.
- **Advertise participation:** E-Mails were sent out to participants of previous issues of ECER. ER4STEM partners also contacted their school partners to advertise for participation.
- **Link to WP2:** First planning of the Botball workshop for participating teams was done.

Performed tasks of Phase 2:

- **Participation at Botball Instructors' Summit at the KISS Institute of Practical Robotics (KIPR), Oklahoma, USA:** As ECER hosts the official European Championship in Botball, every year one representative of PRIA participated at the Botball Instructors' Summit to obtain information about that season's rules and Botball set. Furthermore, details regarding the registration process and shipment of robotic sets to the participants were clarified with KIPR.
- **Delivery of Botball sets:** PRIA arranged the delivery of Botball sets for most Botball teams and also supported in the delivery of sets to teams competing in the other competitions. Botball sets are required if a team wants to participate in the official Botball tournament.
- **Contact with participants:** PRIA, ESI CEE, AL and other country organisers were in regular contact with the participants of ECER for supporting in various matters ranging from the writing of papers to technical issues with the robotics sets.
- **Botball workshop (WP2):** Every year, one Botball workshop at PRIA was prepared and carried out. Information from the Botball Instructors' Summit was thus passed on to the Austrian teams. In 2017, ESI CEE also carried out this workshop for Bulgarian teams with the assistance of PRIA via a telepresence robot. Workshops for teams of other countries (not within the scope of ER4STEM) were also carried out. Some teams received support via skype connection.
- **Organisation of resources for ECER:** Three game tables were organized for each ECER for the Botball and open tournaments. A cage for the aerial tournament was assembled. Name tags and printed handouts for the ECER participants were prepared. Spare Botball parts were organised to replace any breakages in participants Botball sets during the competition. T-shirts were designed and printed for participants to purchase. EU funding was promoted and visualized in advertising and information materials.
- **Organisation of invited talks:** The invited talks were given by researchers that were known to the organisers. For instance Prof. David Miller is the founder of the Botball program and was happy to visit ECER 2018 in Malta to give a talk about other research that he and his team conduct.
- **Submission and review of student papers:** Papers were submitted by each team, with some of them having sole authors and others by groups of authors. All papers were reviewed by at least two researchers and a certain number of papers was selected to be presented. The best of these selected papers were chosen to be presented in a special session at RIE in order to have also the established researchers as audience.
- **Detailed planning of ECER schedule:** According to the accepted papers, the invited talks and the planned tournaments, the ECER schedule was created (see example in Section 2.2).
- **Planning of staff:** Staff were planned for operating the registration desk as well as a support desk. Moreover, additional people acted as judges and fulfilled various other tasks during ECER. In all ECER issues, a number of school students acted as volunteers for supporting the event.
- **Preparation of invitation letters:** Some participants (from Egypt, Iran and Kuwait) needed Visa for entering European Union, which required invitation letters. Also invitation letters were issued for other participants when required.

2.3 SCHEDULE

The following example schedule was taken from ECER 2018:

Monday, April 16th		
13:00-14:00	Registration	
14:00-16:30	Open Practice Qualification & Practice	
16:30-17:00	Opening Ceremony	
Tuesday, April 17th		
08:30-10:15	Open Practice	
10:15-12:00	Botball & Open: Seeding Round 1	
12:00-13:00	Lunch Break	
13:00-14:00	Student Talks	
14:00-15:00	Open Practice	
15:00-17:00	Botball & Open: Seeding Rounds 2 & 3	Underwater Tournament
17:00-18:00	Invited Talk	
Wednesday, April 18th		
08:30-12:00	Open Practice	Onsite Presentation (from 09:00)
10:00-12:00	Aerial Tournament	
12:00-13:00	Lunch Break	
13:00-14:00	Student Talks (RiE student session)	
14:00-16:30	Botball & Open: Double Elimination	
16:30-17:30	Invited Talk	
Thursday, April 19th		
08:30-12:00	Open Practice	Robot Showcases
12:00-13:00	Lunch Break	
13:00-14:00	Student Talks	
14:00-17:00	Open Practice	Aerial & Underwater Tournament
17:00-18:00	Dinner Break	
18:00-20:00	Open Practice Disco	
Friday, April 20th		
08:30-10:30	Botball & Open: Finals & Alliances	
11:00-12:30	Awards Ceremony	

2.4 PARTICIPANTS

Together the issues 2016, 2017 and 2018 of ECER had more than 500 participants from the following countries:

- Albania
- Austria
- Belgium
- Bulgaria
- Croatia
- Egypt
- Malta
- Kuwait
- Poland

Participants from Iran also registered for the conference 2017 and from the Philippines for ECER 2018 but unfortunately they did not attend – reasons were not communicated.

Furthermore, as the International Conference on Robotics in Education (RiE) was hosted in parallel to ECER in the years 2016, 2017 and 2018, the attendants of RiE had the chance to visit ECER. As a consequence, the three ECER's saw a total of around 150 international visitors from the following countries:

- Austria
- Belgium
- Brazil
- Bulgaria
- China
- Croatia
- Czech Republic
- Finland
- France
- Germany
- Greece
- Israel
- Italy
- Japan
- Lebanon
- Malta
- Netherlands
- Poland
- Portugal
- Qatar
- Russia
- Slovakia
- Slovenia
- Spain
- Sweden
- Switzerland
- Thailand+
- Turkey
- UK
- USA

Furthermore, several classes from middle and primary schools took the chance of visiting ECER as they were invited prior to the conference about this exciting event. This allowed the young pupils to see possibilities of engagement in STEM and robotics in particular.

3 PROCESS OF THE CONFERENCE IMPLEMENTATION

This section provides a generalised process for implementing a conference for students, which is based on the experience gained from the organisation of multiple ECER events (presented in section 2). The according process steps and necessary decisions were derived and are presented in this section. Section 3.1 gives an overview on the process plan, which contains various steps. Sections 3.2-3.5 then present details on each of these steps using the following structure:

- **Description:** Text for describing the step
- **Entry criteria:** Condition needed for starting this step
- **Inputs:** Material or information required for carrying out this step
- **Outputs:** Material or information created or obtained after carrying out this step
- **Exit criteria:** Condition needed for ending this step

3.1 PROCESS PLAN

Fig. 1 shows an overview of the generic process for educational robotics conference organization. As can be seen, the process is divided into 4 phases each comprising various activities. A detailed description of these activities is provided in the following sections.

Fig. 1: Generic process for educational robotics conference organisation

3.2 INITIATION

□ Obtain commitment about the host

Description

Find a reliable partner that will host the conference and inform them about the necessary organization requirements and activities.

Entry criteria

A conference shall be organized

Inputs

Materials and feedback from previous conferences

Outputs

General agreement about organizing the conference

Exit criteria

Commitment about hosting the conference obtained

Define topic

Description

Generally the ECER carried out during ER4STEM is centered on robotics as main topic but of course such a conference design could be used in another domain as well. Furthermore a specific focus topic (e.g. robotics in agriculture) can be defined for each conference issue in order to give that year's conference a certain meaning.

Entry criteria

Host committed to organize the conference

Inputs

- Current trends in educational robotics
- Specific topics brought by the host

Outputs

List of key topics

Exit criteria

Relevant stakeholders agree on the key topics

3.3 PREPARATION

Plan conference activities

Description

A conference can encompass one or more types of activities for its attendees. Based on ECER, the activities can be as follows (but other activities can also be implemented)

- Competition/tournament
- Invited talks – researchers, or also talented student (groups)
- Paper submissions and presentations
- Showcases/booths

Entry criteria

Agreement about the conference topics

Inputs

- Topics
- Target groups
- Specific objectives of the host
- Updated rules of the tournament

Outputs

Activity plan

Exit criteria

Relevant stakeholders agree on the plan for the conference

Plan Conference Resources

Description

- Venue: The venue needs to suit the requirements of the planned activities and estimated size of the conference.
 - Competition/tournament: Space is required for the tournament area, which may need to be quite large depending on the type of competition. For instance, a competition with drones can encompass quite a wide area. Furthermore, the competition area should be suited for people watching the tournament, e.g. team members of the currently competing teams, their teachers, other teams, other visitors (school classes).
 - Talks: A setting suitable for having talks is required, which can be a classroom-type setting up to an auditorium. Of course also restaurant-like settings are imaginable as long as it is ensured that the focus of the listening students is directed towards the speaker. The area for talks can also be used for opening or awards ceremonies.
 - Showcases/booths: In case of showcases or booths, well-accessible space is required for ensuring that conference attendees indeed find and visit the showcase/boot.
 - Work area: A competition offers commonly sufficient time to do last fixes and improvements to the competition equipment, e.g. a robot, or its programming. Consequently, in the case of several hundred participants, a work area large enough needs to be set up that encompasses necessities such as electrical outlets or WIFI.
- Budget: A budget needs to be planned, which should encompass expenditures such as venue rent, logistics, technical equipment (e.g. electrical outlets), staff costs, travel costs, PR.
- Funding: The planned budget needs to be covered by funding, which can encompass the following sources:
 - Grants: They can be available ranging from European, state, down to regional level. Grants have the advantage of a quite secure funding once permitted but the funding rate tends to be below 100% and there is no guarantee for getting a positive evaluation. Evaluation durations can be up to some months, which is why the work on grants needs to start very early. Grants can involve significant administrative work.
 - Sponsoring: Financial sponsoring but also the sponsoring of other resources (equipment, manpower) is possible. Financial sponsoring is commonly a distinct amount of money, which does not involve administrative work once a positive decision was made by a sponsor. Finding possible sponsors and convincing them to spend money is the elaborate task in this way of funding. Sponsors commonly want some type of benefit, e.g. their logo on printed materials and on an event website or being able to hold a talk at the conference.
 - Registration fees: Fees represent reliable money but can be troublesome regarding limited student (or family) budget thus limiting the competition possibly to more privileged students. In the case of a registration fee, it must be set to a level that students and their families are willing and capable to pay.

- Merchandise: Items can be sold at the conference as another source of money. Likewise to the registration fees, the price of the items needs to be set to a level that students are willing and capable to pay.

Entry criteria

Activities are planned

Inputs

Activity plan

Outputs

Detailed activity plan including plan of the needed resources

Exit criteria

Detailed activity plan is proposed to the relevant stakeholders.

◆ Commitment to the plan and budget is obtained

NO: Return to Plan conference activities

YES: Go to Awareness Campaign

Awareness Campaign

Description

- The aim of the awareness campaign is to make possible attendees aware of the conference in order to win them as actual participants. Various channels can be included, which require different amounts of budget and personnel resources:
 - Website
 - Social media
 - Printed materials
 - Newsletters
 - Multipliers (other entities/persons that spread the word)

Entry criteria

Plan and budget accepted by all relevant stakeholders

Inputs

Detailed activity plan

Outputs

Students, teachers and volunteers confirm their participation in the conference.

Exit criteria

Conference starts in two weeks.

3.4 EXECUTION

Student papers

Description

This activity tackles the process of the student paper submission and review prior to the conference, which is likewise to scientific conference submission processes. When a “call for papers” is available, the participants can submit initial paper versions. Reviewers should be selected that then review the submissions according to provided review criteria. It can then be decided if all or only selected papers will be presented at the conference (at ECER only selected papers). Once the review is sent to the authors, they can improve the papers and submit final paper versions.

Entry criteria

Student papers are part of the conference activities and a “call for papers” is made available and participants are willing to submit papers.

Inputs

- Call for papers
- Initial paper submissions

Outputs

Final papers

Exit criteria

Final versions of papers are submitted

Tournament preparation

Description

The rules for the competition can either be derived from existing initiatives or created from scratch. A key for a successful competition is the possibility for all participants to achieve at least a certain amount of success. In order to avoid ambiguities, the rules need to be defined precisely and in an easy form to understand. Most likely, the rules should be communicated to the participants before the conference so that preparation time is ensured. Ongoing contact with the participants might then be needed in order to support them during their preparation for the competition.

Entry criteria

Competitions are part of the conference activities.

Inputs

- Planned types of tournaments
- Available competition rules (optional)

Outputs

- Competition rules

Exit criteria

Competition rules are decided and participants are informed

Detailed planning

Description

This activity encompasses the detailed planning activities for ensuring that the conference is ready to be carried out. The organizers need to make sure that enough personnel is available for various tasks at the conference (support of participants, technical matters, competition judges, etc.). Required physical materials such as competition game tables, tables and chairs for the participants, projector, sound system, name badges, etc. need to be obtained. Participants from certain countries might need invitation letters in order to get a visa. Decisions about speakers for invited talks and showcases/booths have to be made and according budget (for travel or transport costs) might need to be foreseen. Means of evaluation possibilities can be developed as an evaluation can deliver on the one hand insights regarding the effectiveness of the conference regarding its aims (e.g. changing attitudes to STEM) or on the other hand lessons learned for improving successor events.

Entry criteria

Participation at conference is ensured.

Inputs

- Detailed activity plan
- Available budget

Outputs

- Conference material
- Staff plan
- Schedule
- Invitation letters
- Invited talks
- Accepted showcases/booths
- Evaluation method

Exit criteria

All preparations prior to the conference are considered completed.

Carrying out the conference

Description

Having setup time before the start of the conference is required and consequently having a complete setup day is advisable. The conference rooms need to be arranged and the special installations (e.g. game table, cage for aerial tournaments, etc.) are built. Then the conference is carried out according to the conference schedule and the planned activities. Support for the participants is to be provided. In parallel the evaluation activities can be conducted. After a possible award ceremony at the end of the conference, the special equipment can be disassembled.

Entry criteria

One day before the conference

Inputs

- Detailed activity plan
- Conference schedule

Outputs

Participants gain knowledge and experience in educational robotics

Exit criteria

Last day of the conference

3.5 CLOSURE

Evaluate results

Description

Based on the gathered data from evaluation carried out during the conference, the results are analyzed in terms of activities, budget and impact to the main target groups according to the objectives of the conference.

Entry criteria

Conference completed

Inputs

- Conference objectives
- Detailed activity plan
- Evaluation method
- Evaluation artifacts from the conference

Outputs

Conference report

Exit criteria

Evaluation completed

4 CONCLUSION / OUTLOOK

This deliverable describes a generic plan on how to organize a student conference based on the three issues of ECER that were carried out in the frame of the project ER4STEM. Consequently, Section 2 reports on the performed activities for organizing and carrying out ECER. In Section 3 the derived conference plan is presented.

The conference plan provides a sequence of activities that should be performed by conference organizers prior to the actual event. Despite being intended for conferences with a technical topic like educational robotics, the described organization process can also generally be viewed as guideline for any student conference.

5 GLOSSARY / ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
ECER	European Conference on Educational Robotics
ER4STEM	Educational Robotics for STEM
KIPR	KISS Institute of Practical Robotics
KISS	Keep it simple, stupid; also variations exist, e.g. keep it short and simple
REA	Research Executive Agency
RiE	International Conference on Robotics in Education
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics

